

ENGLISH EDUCATION

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Fundamentals of Language and Linguistics

Course number	: Eng Ed 3001	Course duration	: 150 hrs
Nature of the course	: Theoretical	Number of periods	: 180
Full mark	: 100	Periods per week	: 6
Pass mark	: 35	Time per period	: 50 min

Course Description

This is an introductory but comprehensive course on the fundamentals of language and linguistics and their applications to language teaching. The course consists of six units. The first two units present fundamental concepts of language and linguistics. The next three units deal with the three core areas of linguistics - Phonology, Grammar and Semantics - corresponding to the three fundamental aspects of language - sounds, forms and meanings. The last unit deals with applications of linguistics to language teaching.

As the course has been designed primarily for the purpose of training teachers of English, all the contents of the course are specifically related to the English language and its teaching in Nepal.

General Objective

The course aims at providing the teacher trainees with a sound knowledge of what language is and how it works. In addition, it tries to acquaint them with the processes and difficulties involved in learning a second language, particularly with the difficulties encountered by Nepali learners of English, and suggest measures to overcome them.

Specific Objectives

On completion of the course the trainees will be acquainted with

- the fundamental concepts of language and linguistics.
- the basic dichotomies in language and linguistics.
- the fundamental aspects of the phonological, grammatical and semantic systems of language, particularly those of the English language.

- the applications of linguistics to language teaching in general and with principal theoretical bases and basic techniques of Contrastive Analysis and Error Analysis in particular.

In addition, they will be able to

- identify, describe, classify and produce the sounds of English in isolation and in connected speech.
- comprehend spoken English with greater ease and speak English in a better way.
- carry out simple contrastive analysis and error analysis and use the findings of these analyses to orient their teaching to the main areas of difficulties encountered by the language learners.

Course contents	(27 periods)
Unit 1 : Nature of Language	(27 periods)
Unit 2 : Dichotomies in Language	(36 periods)
Unit 3 : Sounds of Language	(36 periods)
Unit 4 : Forms of Language	(18 periods)
Unit 5 : Meaning in Language	
Unit 6 : Applications of Linguistics to Language Teaching	(36 periods)

Course Contents in Detail

- Unit 1: Nature of Language**
- 1.1 Definition of linguistics
 - 1.2 Definition of language
 - 1.3 Characteristics of language
 - 1.4 Language and animal communication
 - 1.5 Language as a system of systems
 - 1.6 Levels of language
 - 1.7 Varieties of language
 - 1.7.1 Dialects, registers and idiolects
 - 1.7.2 British and American English
 - 1.7.3 Formal and informal English

- Unit 2: Dichotomies in Language**
- 2.1 Langue and parole
 - 2.2 Competence and performance

- 2.3
- 2.4
- 2.5
- 2.6
- 2.7
- 2.8
- 2.9
- 2.10
- 2.11

Unit 3: Sound

- 3.1
- 3.2

3.3

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- 2.3 Synchronic study and diachronic study
 - 2.4 Syntagmatic relation and paradigmatic relation
 - 2.5 Speech and writing
 - 2.6 Orthographic writing and phonemic writing
 - 2.7 Broad transcription and narrow transcription
 - 2.8 Descriptive grammar and prescriptive grammar
 - 2.9 Content words and function words
 - 2.10 Lexical meaning and grammatical meaning
 - 2.11 Syllable-timed language and stress-timed language

Unit 3: Sounds of Language

- 3.1 Organs of speech
- 3.2 Classification of sounds
 - 3.2.1 Segmental sounds: vowels and consonants
 - 3.2.2 Suprasegmental features: length, stress and pitch
- 3.3 English Vowels
 - 3.3.1 Inventory (*detailed list*)
 - 3.3.2 Classification of vowels: monophthongs and diphthongs
 - 3.3.3 Description of monophthongs
 - high, mid, low (*in terms of the height of the tongue*)
 - front, central, back (" " " position " " ")
 - rounded and unrounded (*lip form*)
 - short and long (*length*)
 - 3.3.4 Description of diphthongs
 - closing and centring
 - 3.3.5 Correlation between sounds, symbols, descriptions and spellings
- 3.4 English Consonants
 - 3.4.1 Inventory
 - 3.4.2 Three-term description
 - ① - voicing: voiced and voiceless
 - ② - place of articulation: bilabial, labio-dental, dental, alveolar, palato-alveolar, palatal, velar, glottal
 - ③ - manner of articulation: stop, nasal, fricative, affricate, lateral, frictionless continuant, semi-vowel
 - 3.4.3 Variations of voiceless stops and lateral

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- 3.4.4 Correlation between sounds, symbols, descriptions and spellings
- 3.5 Consonant clusters
 - 3.5.1 Word-initial clusters
 - 3.5.2 Word-final clusters
 - 3.5.3 Word-medial clusters
 - intrasyllabic clusters
 - intersyllabic clusters
- 3.6 Vowel sequences
- 3.7 Syllable structures: (C) (C) (C) V (C) (C) (C) (C) or C₀₋₃ VC₀₋₄
- 3.8 Stress and rhythm
 - 3.8.1 Word stress
 - 3.8.2 Sentence stress (Rhythm)
- 3.9 Intonation
 - 3.9.1 Tune shapes
 - the falling tune : the glide-down
 - the first rising tune : the glide-up
 - the second rising tune : the take-off
 - the falling-rising tune : the dive
 - 3.9.2 Uses of the tunes
- 3.10 Words in connected speech
 - 3.10.1 Strong forms and weak forms
 - 3.10.2 Linking 'r' and intrusive 'r'
 - 3.10.3 Pronunciation of the suffixes '-s', '-es' and '-ed'
 - 3.10.4 Alterations and disappearances of sounds

Unit 4: Forms of Language

- 4.1 Basic concepts
 - 4.1.1 Grammatical units
 - morpheme, word, phrase, clause, sentence
 - 4.1.2 Grammatical structures
 - structures of words, phrases, clauses, sentences
 - 4.1.3 Grammatical functions
 - subject, predicate, object, complement, adjunct
 - 4.1.4 Grammatical categories
 - gender, number, person, case, tense, aspect, mood, voice
 - 4.1.5 Grammatical transformations
 - negation, question, passivisation, contraction

Unit 5: M

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4.1.6 Grammatical operations/devices
- insertion, deletion, transposition, substitution

4.2 Morphology and syntax

4.2.1 The morpheme

- free and bound morphemes
- morpheme and its allomorphs

4.2.2 The word

- Word types: orthographic, morphological, lexical, semantic
- Word classes
- major: noun, verb, adjective, adverb
- minor: pronoun, preposition, conjunction, interjection, intensifier, classifier, determiner (article, numeral, quantifier, demonstrative, possessive)
- Word formation
- affixation (prefixation, suffixation), compounding, reduplication, coinage, blending, back formation, acronymy
- inflection and derivation

4.2.3 The phrase

- Types and functions of phrases

4.2.4 The clause

- Types and functions of clauses

4.2.5 The sentence

- Types of sentences
- functional: declarative, imperative, interrogative, optative, exclamatory
- structural: simple, compound, complex, compound-complex

Unit 5: Meaning in Language

5.1 Synonymy

5.1.1 Intralingual and interlingual synonymy

5.1.2 Absolute and partial synonymy

5.2 Antonymy

5.2.1 Gradable antonymy

5.2.2 Complementarity and incompatibility

5.2.3 Converseness

- 5.3 Hyponymy
 - 5.3.1 Hypernym (Superordinate term) and hyponym
 - 5.3.2 Co-hyponyms
- 5.4 Homonymy
 - 5.4.1 Homophony and homography
 - 5.4.2 Lexical and grammatical homonymy
 - 5.4.3 Homonymy and polisemy
- 5.5 Idioms
- 5.6 Semantic overlapping

Unit 6 : Applications of Linguistics to Language Teaching

- 6.1 General applications
 - 6.1.1 Provision of insight into the nature of language
 - 6.1.2 Provision of descriptions of languages
 - 6.1.3 Removal of misconceptions about language and language learning/teaching
- 6.2 Contrastive analysis
 - 6.2.1 Definition
 - 6.2.2 CA hypothesis: difference - interference- error similarity - facilitation - no error
 - 6.2.3 Practical contrastive analysis of some aspects of English and Nepali and prediction of difficulties for Nepali learners of English
- 6.3 Error analysis
 - 6.3.1 Mistake and error
 - 6.3.2 Types of error
 - individual and group errors
 - receptive and productive errors
 - overt and covert errors
 - graphological, phonological, grammatical (morphological, syntactic), semantic or lexical and stylistic errors
 - 6.3.3 Causes or sources of errors
 - 6.3.4 Correction and remediation of errors
 - 6.3.5 Practical error analysis of the texts produced by Nepali learners of English Instructional Techniques
 - Lecture, explanation and illustration
 - Demonstration and discussion
 - Individual and group work/project
 - Self study

Assessment Techn
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Prescribed Text

1. Sthapit, S.
Linguistics.

References

1. Allen, J. P.
Oxford: Ox
2. Allen, J. P.
Linguistics
3. Bolinger, I
World, 196
4. Corder, S.
Penguin B
5. Crystal, D
6. Edge, J. M
7. Gimson, A
Edward A
8. Halliday,
Sciences
1964.
9. Jackson, J
10. Kansakar
Longmar
11. Leech, C
1975.
12. Lyons, J.
Press, 19

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Assessment Technique and Mark Distribution
Written examination : 100 marks

Unitwise mark distribution

Units 1, 2 and 6 : 50 marks
Units 3, 4 and 5 : 50 marks

Questionwise mark distribution

20 multiple-choice questions : $20 \times 1 = 20$ marks
2 long-answer questions : $2 \times 12 = 24$ marks
8 short-answer questions : $8 \times 7 = 56$ marks

Prescribed Textbook

1. Sthapit, S. K. and S. Basnyat. *Fundamentals of Language and Linguistics*. (Forthcoming)

References

1. Allen, J. P. B. and S. P. Corder (eds). *Papers in Applied Linguistics*. Oxford: Oxford University Press, 1975.
2. Allen, J. P. B. and S. P. Corder (eds). *Techniques in Applied Linguistics*. Oxford: Oxford University Press, 1974.
3. Bolinger, D. *Aspects of Language*. New York: Harcourt, Brace and World, 1968.
4. Corder, S. P. *Introducing Applied Linguistics*. Harmondsworth: Penguin Books, 1973.
5. Crystal, D. *Linguistics*. Harmondsworth: Penguin Books, 1973.
6. Edge, J. *Mistakes and Correction*. London: Longman, 1993.
7. Gimson, A. C. *Introduction to the Pronunciation of English*. London: Edward Arnold, 1970.
8. Halliday, M. A. K., A. McIntosh and P. Stevens. *The Linguistic Sciences and Language Teaching*. London: ELBS and Longman, 1964.
9. Jackson, H. *Analyzing English*. Oxford: Pergamon Press, 1982.
10. Kansakar, T. R. *A Course in English Phonetics*. Madras: Orient Longman, 1998.
11. Leech, G. *Communicative Grammar of English*. Essex: Longman, 1975.
12. Lyons, J. *Theoretical Linguistics*. Cambridge: Cambridge University Press, 1968.

13. Lyons, J. Language and Linguistics. Cambridge: Cambridge University Press, 1981.
14. O'Connor, J. D. Better English Pronunciation. Cambridge: Cambridge University Press, 1967.
15. Palmer, F. Grammar. Harmondsworth: Penguin Books, 1971.
16. Todd, L. An Introduction to Linguistics. London: Longman York Press, 1987.
17. Wilkins, D. A. Linguistics in Language Teaching. London: Edward Arnold, 1972.

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English Sounds, Words and Structures

Course number	: Eng Ed 3002	Course duration	: 150 hrs
Nature of the course	: Theoretical cum practical	Number of periods	: 180
Full mark	: 100	Periods per week	: 6
Pass mark	: Th: 35 % & Pr: 40 %	Time per period	: 50 min

Course Description

This is a course on the sounds, words and structures of the English language. Correspondingly, the course is divided into three units. The first unit deals with spoken English, particularly with pronunciation practice, the second unit is concerned with English vocabulary, particularly with its semantic aspect and the third unit focuses on the structures and functions of grammatical units.

The course is of theoretical cum practical nature. While the first unit is practical, the other two are theoretical. The theoretical part will be examined in written form whereas the practical part will be examined in spoken form, and the students are required to pass both the parts separately.

General Objective

The course aims at improving the teacher trainees' command of the English language so that they can use the language fluently, aptly and correctly.

Specific Objectives

On completion of the course the trainees will be able to

- improve their spoken English so that they can better understand native English and speak the language with better pronunciation and fluency and with greater confidence.
- expand the repertoire of their English vocabulary, learn the techniques of enriching it and use it appropriately.
- gain deeper insight into English grammar, develop their skills in syntactic argumentation and use the language correctly.

(72 periods)
(36 periods)
(72 periods)

- 1.6 Pronunciation of words with different stress patterns
 - 1.6.1 Two-syllable words
 - 1.6.2 Three-syllable words
 - 1.6.3 Words with more than three syllables
- 1.7 Pronunciation of sentences with different stress patterns
- 1.8 Pronunciation of sentences with different intonation patterns
 - 1.8.1 Sentences with falling tune
 - 1.8.2 Sentences with first rising tune
 - 1.8.3 Sentences with second rising tune
 - 1.8.4 Sentences with falling-rising tune
- 1.9 Pronunciation of words in connected speech
 - 1.9.1 Strong and weak forms of function words
 - 1.9.2 Linking and intrusive 'r'
 - 1.9.3 The suffixes '-s', '-es' and '-ed'
 - 1.9.4 Words with elision of sounds
 - 1.9.5 Words with assimilation of sounds
 - 1.9.6 Words with coalescence of sounds

Unit 2: The Words of English

- 2.1 Words for mature minds
- 2.2 Words about doctors and specialists
- 2.3 Verbs that give you power
- 2.4 Words about theories
- 2.5 Vocabulary builder
- 2.6 Words about your fellowmen
- 2.7 Words for phobias and manias
- 2.8 Words about your feelings
- 2.9 Words that end in "ology"
- 2.10 Words for human traits
- 2.11 Words for human faults
- 2.12 Words about personalities
- 2.13 Adjectives that give you power
- 2.14 Learning words the modern way
- 2.15 Words from Latin
- 2.16 Guessing the meaning of words from the context
- 2.17 Words that describe you
- 2.18 French phrases you can use
- 2.19 Words about words
- 2.20 Word building by the "unfolding process"

- 2.21 Words from classic roots
2.22 Words change their meanings

Unit 3: **The Structures of English**

- 3.1 The morpheme
3.1.1 Introduction
3.1.2 Free and bound morphemes
3.1.3 Morpheme and its allomorphs
3.1.4 Affixes: prefixes and suffixes
3.1.5 Inflectional and derivational affixes
- 3.2 The word
3.2.1 Introduction
3.2.2 Word classes
- nouns
 - adjectives
 - adverbs
 - verbs
 - prepositions
 - conjunctions
 - articles
 - numerals
 - pronouns
 - personal pronouns
 - self-pronouns
 - demonstrative pronouns
 - possessive pronouns
 - relative pronouns
 - interrogative pronouns
 - reciprocal pronouns
 - 'so' and 'one'
 - quantifiers
 - interjections
- 3.3 The phrase
3.3.1 Introduction
3.3.2 The noun phrase
3.3.3 The adjective phrase
3.3.4 The adverb phrase
3.3.5 The verb phrase
3.3.6 The prepositional phrase

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- 3.4 The sentence
- 3.4.1 Introduction
 - 3.4.2 The simple sentence
 - 3.4.3 Combining and condensing sentences
 - subordination and coordination
 - the complex sentence
 - the compound sentence
 - substitution and ellipsis
 - substitution
 - ellipsis
 - 3.4.4 Negation and the formation of questions
 - negation
 - the formation of questions
 - 3.4.5 Grammatical form and function in communication
 - sentences and their grammatical form
 - sentences and their function in communication
 - 3.4.6 Sentences and the organisation of the message
 - focus
 - word order
 - cleft sentences and pseudo-cleft sentences
- 3.5 The structure of the word
- 3.5.1 Affixation
 - 3.5.2 Compounding
- 3.6 The structure of the phrase
- 3.6.1 The noun phrase
 - determiner
 - pre-modifier
 - post-modifier
 - discontinuous modifier
 - 3.6.2 The adjective phrase
 - pre-modifier
 - post-modifier
 - discontinuous modifier
 - 3.6.3 The adverb phrase
 - pre-modifier
 - post-modifier
 - discontinuous modifier
 - 3.6.4 The verb phrase
 - 3.6.5 The prepositional phrase

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3.7 The structure of the sentence: functions

3.7.1 Introduction

3.7.2 Subject

3.7.3 Predicate

- predicator
- complement
- direct object
- indirect object
- benefactive object
- subject attribute
- object attribute
- predicator complement

3.7.4 Adverbial

3.8 The structure of the sentence: realizations

3.8.1 Introduction

3.8.2 Subject

3.8.3 Predicate

- predicator
- complement
- direct object
- indirect object
- benefactive object
- subject attribute
- object attribute
- predicator complement

3.8.4 Adverbial

Instructional Techniques

- Lecture, explanation and illustration
- Demonstration and dramatization
- Drill and discussion
- Individual and group work/project
- Self study and practice

Assessment Technique and Mark Distribution

Written examination : 60 marks

(Pass mark : 21)

Unitwise mark distribution

Units 2 : 20 marks

Units 3 : 40 marks

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Questionwise mark distribution

20 multiple-choice questions	: 12 x 1 = 12 marks
2 long-answer questions	: 2 x 8 = 16 marks
8 short-answer questions	: 8 x 4 = 32 marks

Practical examination : 40 marks

(Pass mark : 16)

Unitwise distribution of marks :

Units 1 : 40 marks

Questionwise distribution of marks :

Listening comprehension : 10 marks

Reading aloud : 10 marks

Interview : 20 mark

Prescribed Textbooks

1. Aarts, F. and J. Aarts. English Syntactic Structures. Oxford: Pergamon Press, 1986.
2. Aarts, F. and J. Aarts. English Syntactic Structures: Workbook. Englewood: Prentice Hall International, 1987.
3. Funk, W. and N. Lewis. 30 Days to a More Powerful Vocabulary. New York: Pocket Books, 1971.
4. O'Connor, J. D. Better English Pronunciation. Cambridge: Cambridge University Press, 1967.

References

1. Brown, G. Listening to Spoken English. London: Longman, 1977.
2. Gimson, A. C. An Introduction to the Pronunciation of English. London: Edward Arnold, 1970.
3. Kansakar, T. R. A Course in English Phonetics. Hyderabad: Orient Longman, 1998.
4. Sthapit, S. K. and S. Basnyat. Fundamentals of Language and Linguistics. (Forthcoming)
5. Todd, L. An Introduction to Linguistics. London: Longman, 1987

✓✓ ELT Methods and Activities

Course number : Eng Ed 3003
Nature of the course : Theoretical
Full mark : 100
Pass mark : 35

Course duration : 150 hrs
Number of periods : 180
Periods per week : 6
Time per period : 50 min

Course Description

This is a course on English language teaching methods and activities particularly geared to teaching English as a foreign language in Nepal. The course consists of twelve units. The first unit presents the fundamentals of language learning and teaching. The second unit deals with language teaching approaches, methods and techniques. The next nine units deal with various practical aspects of ELT pedagogy. The last unit deals with testing and evaluation in considerable detail.

General objective

The course aims at providing the teacher trainees with an insight into different aspects of ELT methodology and helping them acquire various pedagogical skills in ELT.

Specific Objectives

On completion of the course the trainees will be acquainted with

- the fundamentals of language learning and teaching.
 - language teaching approaches, methods and techniques in general.
 - the methods and techniques of teaching graphology, vocabulary and grammar.
 - the methods and techniques of teaching the four basic skills of language.
 - language teaching aids and materials and their functions and values in language teaching.
 - the concepts related to planning language teaching.
 - the concepts and techniques of language testing and evaluation.
- In addition, they will be able to
- carry out pedagogical activities geared to teaching English

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Unit

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Unit

- graphology, vocabulary and grammar.
- carry out pedagogical activities geared to teaching English language skills.
- collect or construct audio-visual aids and other related teaching materials and use them in teaching English effectively.
- make annual work plans, unit plans and daily lesson plans for efficient and effective teaching of English.
- Design, construct and use different types of tests, particularly in relation to the learning and teaching of the English language.
- administer and evaluate tests and interpret their results scientifically.

Course Contents

Unit 1: Fundamentals of Language Learning and Teaching	(5 periods)
Unit 2: Language Teaching Approaches, Methods and Techniques	(30 periods)
Unit 3: Teaching Graphology	(10 periods)
Unit 4: Teaching Vocabulary	(10 periods)
Unit 5: Teaching Grammar	(10 periods)
Unit 6: Teaching Listening	(10 periods)
Unit 7: Teaching Speaking	(10 periods)
Unit 8: Teaching Reading	(15 periods)
Unit 9: Teaching Writing	(25 periods)
Unit 10: Teaching Aids and Materials	(20 periods)
Unit 11: Planning Teaching	(10 periods)
Unit 12: Testing and Evaluation	(25 periods)

Course Contents in Detail

Unit 1: Fundamentals of Language Learning and Teaching
1.1 Teaching-learning relationship
1.2 Facilitation of learning
1.3 Teacher's role
1.4 Quality of a good English teacher
1.5 Stages of language learning/teaching
1.6 Learning L1 and learning L2
1.7 Aspects and skills of language

Unit 2: Language Teaching Approaches, Methods and Techniques

- 2.1 Three levels of operation of language teaching scheme
- 2.2 General approaches/methods
 - 2.2.1 Deductive and inductive approaches/methods
 - 2.2.2 Teacher-centred and learner-centred approaches/methods
- 2.3 Specific approaches/methods: (theoretical bases, characteristic features and strengths and weaknesses of)
 - 2.3.1 The grammar-translation method
 - 2.3.2 The audio-lingual method / The OSS approach
 - 2.3.3 The communicative approach
- 2.4 Techniques
 - 2.4.1 Teacher-centred techniques
 - 2.4.2 Learner-centred techniques
- 2.5 Drills
 - 2.5.1 Definition and functions of a drill
 - 2.5.2 Classification of drills
 - 2.5.3 Preparation and practice of drills

Unit 3: Teaching Graphology

- 3.1 Writing systems
- 3.2 English graphology
- 3.3 Teaching English punctuation and its use

Unit 4: Teaching Vocabulary

- 4.1 Characterisation of vocabulary
- 4.2 Aspects of learning/teaching a vocabulary item
- 4.3 Techniques of teaching vocabulary
- 4.4 Consolidation and automation of vocabulary learnt

Unit 5: Teaching Grammar

- 5.1 Objectives of teaching grammar
- 5.2 Approaches/Methods of teaching grammar
- 5.3 Stepwise procedure of teaching grammar

Unit 6: Teaching Listening

- 6.1 Components of listening skills
- 6.2 Activities for developing listening skills

Unit 7: 7.1 7.1
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Unit 8: Teaching
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Unit 9: Teaching
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Unit 10: Teaching
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Unit 11: Planning
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Unit 7: **Teaching Speaking**

- 7.1 Components of speaking skills (parts)
7.1.1 Pronunciation skills
7.1.2 Communication skills
7.2 Activities for developing speaking skills

Unit 8: **Teaching Reading**

- 8.1 Characterisation of reading
8.2 Components of reading skills
8.3 Activities for developing reading skills

Unit 9: **Teaching Writing**

- 9.1 Components of writing skills
9.2 Activities for developing writing skills
9.2.1 Controlled writing activities
9.2.2 Guided writing activities
9.2.3 Independent writing activities

Unit 10: **Teaching Aids and Materials**

- 10.1 Teaching aids
10.1.1 Definition
10.1.2 Types
10.1.3 Visual aids
10.1.4 Collection, construction and use of visual aids
10.1.5 Value of teaching aids
10.2 Teaching materials
10.2.1 Curricula and courses of study
10.2.2 Textbooks/Course books
10.2.3 Supplementary materials
10.2.4 Collection, overview and use of teaching materials

Unit 11: **Planning Teaching**

- 11.1 Annual work plan
11.2 Unit plan
11.3 Lesson plan
11.3.1 Format of a lesson plan
11.3.2 Construction of lesson plans
11.3.3 Value of lesson planning

Unit 12: Testing and Evaluation

- 12.1 Terminology
- 12.2 Classification of tests
 - 12.2.1 Goal-based types
 - 12.2.2 Medium-based types
 - 12.2.3 Mode-based types
 - 12.2.4 Aspect-based types
 - 12.2.5 Skill-based types
 - 12.2.6 Item-based types
 - 12.2.7 Reference-based types
 - 12.2.8 Deletion-based types
- 12.3 Test design
- 12.4 Marking and scoring
- 12.5 Evaluation of tests
- 12.6 Analysis and interpretation of test results
- 12.7 Test administration
- 12.8 Backwash/Washback effects of tests

Instructional Techniques

- Lecture, explanation and illustration
- Demonstration and discussion
- Simulation and role play
- drilling
- Individual and group work/project
- Self study

Assessment Technique and Mark Distribution

Written examination : 100 marks

Unitwise mark distribution

Units 1, 2, 10, 11 and 12 : 50 marks

Units 3 to 9 : 50 marks

Questionwise mark distribution

20 multiple-choice questions : $20 \times 1 = 20$ marks

2 long-answer questions : $2 \times 12 = 24$ marks

8 short-answer questions : $8 \times 7 = 56$ marks

Prescribed Texts

1. Cross, D. Prentice Hall, 1975.
2. Gordon, L. Books, 1975.
3. Heaton, J. 1975.
4. Larsen, J. Teaching

References

1. Abbott, J. International Journal of Educational Research, 1981.
2. Allen, J. University of Cambridge
3. Brown, J. Cambridge University Press
4. Brown, J. Englewood Cliffs, N.J.
5. Byrne, J.
6. Celce-Murcia, M. Teaching Foreign Languages
7. El-Arabi, M. Longman
8. Grant, J. 1987.
9. Grell, B. University of Cambridge
10. Harmer, J. Longman
11. Harmer, J. 1992.
12. Jupp, J. Heinemann
13. Lee, J. Longman
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Prescribed Textbooks

1. Cross, D. A Practical Handbook of Language Teaching. London: Prentice Hall, 1992.
2. Gordon, I. Practical Punctuation. London: Heinemann Educational Books, 1978.
3. Heaton, J. B. Writing English Language Tests. London: Longman, 1975.
4. Larsen-Freeman, D. Techniques and Principles in Language Teaching. Oxford: Oxford University Press, 1986.

References

1. Abbott, G. and P. Wingard (ed). The Teaching of English as an International Language: A Practical Guide. London: Collins ELT, 1981.
2. Allen, V. F. Techniques in Teaching Vocabulary. Oxford: Oxford University Press, 1983.
3. Brown, G. and G Yule. Teaching the Spoken Language. Cambridge: Cambridge University Press, 1983.
4. Brown, H. D. Principles of Language Learning and Teaching. Englewood Cliffs: Prentice Hall, 1994.
5. Byrne, D. Teaching Writing Skills. London: Longman, 1991.
6. Celce-Murcia, M. and G. Hilles. Techniques and Resources in Teaching Grammar. Oxford: Oxford University Press, 1983.
7. El-Araby, S. A. Audio-visual Aids for Teaching English. London: Longman, 1974.
8. Grant, N. Making the most of your Textbook. London: Longman, 1987.
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10. Harmer, J. The Practice of English Language Teaching. London: Longman, 1991.
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13. Lee, W. R. Language Teaching Games and Contests. London: Longman, 1988.
14. Nunan, D. Designing Tasks for the communicative Classroom. Cambridge University Press, 1989.

Results
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1 = 20 marks
12 = 24 marks
7 = 56 marks

15. Richards, J. J. Platt and H. Weber. Longman Dictionary of Applied Linguistics. London: Longman, 1985.
16. Richards, J. and T. Rodgers. Approaches and Methods in Language Teaching. Cambridge University Press, 1986.
17. Rivers, W. M. Teaching Foreign Language Skills. Chicago: Chicago University Press, 1968.
18. Spencer, D. H. Guided Composition Exercises. London: Longman, 1967.
19. Underwood, M. Teaching Listening. London: Longman, 1989.
20. Wallace, M. J. Teaching Vocabulary. Oxford: Oxford University Press, 1982.
21. White, R. V. Teaching Written English. London: Heinemann Educational Books, 1980.
22. Wright, A. Visual Materials for the Language Teacher. London: Longman, 1990.
23. Wright, A. and S. Halkem. Visuals for the Language Classroom. London: Longman, 1991.
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En

Course number
Nature of the course
Full mark
Pass mark

Course Description
This is a practical course for trainees in this and other courses. It is designed to provide "Student Teaching and Activities" before they go on to the course. The trainee will be expected to implement the course independently.

General Objectives
The course is designed to be completed with first hand experience at the secondary level. Later on they can...

Specific Objectives
On completion of the course the trainee will be able to:
- construct
- collect
- appropriate
- conceive
- activities
- review
- present
- learn
- get the
- they can
- check

✓

एकाइ ३

एकाइ ४, ५

एकाइ ६, ७

अङ्क २०

अङ्क २०

अङ्क २०

प्रश्नगत अंक वितरण

२० वटा बहुविकल्पी प्रश्न

$$२० \times १ = २०$$

२ वटा लामो उत्तर प्रश्न

$$२ \times १२ = २४$$

८ वटा छोटा उत्तर प्रश्न

$$८ \times ७ = ५६$$

3.7 The structure of the sentence: functions

3.7.1 Introduction

3.7.2 Subject

3.7.3 Predicate

- predicator
- complement
- direct object
- indirect object
- benefactive object
- subject attribute
- object attribute
- predicator complement

3.7.4 Adverbial

3.8 The structure of the sentence: realizations

3.8.1 Introduction

3.8.2 Subject

3.8.3 Predicate

- predicator
- complement
- direct object
- indirect object
- benefactive object
- subject attribute
- object attribute
- predicator complement

3.8.4 Adverbial

Instructional Techniques

- Lecture, explanation and illustration
- Demonstration and dramatization
- Drill and discussion
- Individual and group work/project
- Self study and practice

Assessment Technique and Mark Distribution

Written examination : 60 marks

(Pass mark : 21)

Unitwise mark distribution

Units 2 : 20 marks

Units 3 : 40 marks